

PRAGMATIC MEANINGS OF COMPOUNDS IN THE POETRY OF MUKHAMMAD YUSUF

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Abstract: This article reveals the pragmatic meanings and features of compounds used in Muhammad Yusuf's poetry.

Key words: pragmatic unity, linguistic analysis, epiphora, apostrophe, poetic syntax, style, phonetics, poetry.

Introduction.

Today, the analysis of text and poetry has developed as an independent direction in Uzbek linguistics, and a number of works on the linguistic and pragmatic analysis of artistic texts, in particular, the pragmatic study of poetic works, have been given special attention.

Linguistic features of the language of the poetry of the national poet of Uzbekistan Muhammad Yusuf are one of these issues. The poet's poetry has a number of lexical-spiritual and stylistic peculiarities. Therefore, it is necessary to study the lexical-spiritual and methodological aspects of the language of his works. Our research is aimed at filling this gap. The main goal of scientific activity is achieved by performing the following tasks:

- Analyzing the language and style of Muhammad Yusuf's poetry by studying the way in which artistic speech is considered as a manifestation of literary language;
- A review of pragmatic units and their linguistic and cultural research and the conclusions drawn from them in Muhammad Yusuf's poetry;
- To show the importance, types and types of idioms and phraseologisms in the poet's poetry;
- To show the appearance of aphorisms and linguistic and cultural features in the work of the poet;
- Scientific and lexical interpretation of poetic speech in the work of the poet, the means of poetic speech, and showing folk style and originality in the poet's lyrics.

Artistic language is created on the basis of the national language. When the writer uses the universal language, he deviates from the standard norm (*that is, he uses language elements in a different form, meaning, order, relationship, etc.*), and this "deviation" means lum has an artistic-aesthetic goal in mind. Such

deviations can be observed at different levels of the language - phonetic, morphological, lexical, semantic, syntactic levels. Artistic images and means of expression arise as a result of the artist's deviation from the general norm in order to achieve a certain artistic-aesthetic goal. They serve to make the image vivid and full, to increase expressiveness. Deviation from the norm at the lexical level is seen in the writer's use of lexical tools in the national language base. It is known that the words of the national language differ in terms of pictoriality and expressiveness even in the case of fulfilling the nominative task. That is, the creator will be able to enhance the expression and image without affecting the meaning of the word, only by "*choosing words*" from the existing vocabulary. Phrases used in the works of Muhammad Yusuf, the favorite poet of the Uzbek people, have not been the object of complete research.

Muhammad Yusuf's brilliant talent for developing our national literature and culture, raising the spirituality and consciousness of our people, realizing self-awareness in the hearts of the young generation, perfecting the feelings of national pride and pride, noble qualities, unique artistic works, He is a unique creator who made a great contribution with his social activities and arouses wonder and excitement in the hearts of students through his works. Just as there is no unladen fish in a caravan with a clear destination and purpose, in each line of the caravan of words that Muhammad Yusuf sent from his heart to the heart of the nation, there is an incomparable love for the motherland - Uzbekistan, dedication to the service of the people, hardworking and great. It is the embodiment of deep meaning, tone, color and charm, which was created with filial respect, sincerity and passionate passion for the Uzbek people.

Literature analysis (review):

Within the framework of the topic, we analyzed the work of scientists who conducted research activities with the analysis of pragmatic units and linguistic analysis in poetry. *M.Yoqubbekova*¹, *I.Mirzayev*², *S.Karimov*³, *G.Yaxshiyeva*⁴, *A.Abdullayev*⁵, *I.Hojaliyev*⁶, *D.Shodiyeva*⁷, *D. Ne'matova*⁸ works on the linguistic research of the work of Uzbek writers and poets are a clear proof of our opinion.

¹ Yoqubbekova M. Simile in Uzbek folk songs. - Tashkent: Science, 2003. - B.93;

² Mirzaev I.K. Problems of linguistic and poetic interpretation of poetic text: Author's abstract. diss. ... Dr. Philol. Sci. - Tashkent, 1992. - P.52;

³ Karimov S. Artistic style of the Uzbek language: Philol. Ph.D. - Tashkent, 1993. - B.293;

⁴ Yakhasyeva G. Phonographic stylistic tools in the Uzbek language: Philol. subjects nomz. diss. - Tashkent, 1996. - B.132;

⁵ Abdullayev A. The syntactic method of expressiveness in the Uzbek language. - Tashkent: Science, 1987;

⁶ Khojaliyev I. Linguistic features of visual speech type. Philol. sciences nomz... diss. - Fergana, 1998. - B.145;

⁷ Shodiyeva D. Lingupoetics of Muhammad Yusuf's poetry: Philol. sciences nomz... diss. - Tashkent, 2007. - B.144;

⁸ Ne'matova D. Linguistic analysis of Cholpon's journalistic works: Philol. candidate of sciences ... diss. autoref. - Tashkent, 2000.

Despite such achievements, the language and style of the works of poets who created in different periods, and the units in their poems have not been fully linguistically researched.

Discussion:

Mukhammad Yusuf's poetry is considered a real Uzbek poetry. Each of his works shows that he is able to become a powerful and impressive piece when he acquires a complete image, like the creator's personality and poetry. He unhesitatingly accepted the freedom of our country as the answer to the great dream that burned the hearts of great artists like Kadiri and Cholpon. That's why he devoted all his being and talent to singing the national anthem. Another important characteristic of Mukhammad Yusuf's work is the simplicity and folkiness that shines like gold in his poetry. Every line, every stanza of it is decorated with simple, but deep, figurative observations. In any of his poems, you won't find any vague words, ambiguous feelings, illogical expressions, or lightless phrases. He does not always give in to petty feelings. His thoughts are weighty, his expression is gentle, and his feelings are bright. Mukhammad Yusuf perceives life in all its complexities, does not turn a blind eye to the vices and shortcomings of society and people.

Mukhammad Yusuf often appeared in the contemporary press with his prolific work. His first poetry collection was published in 1985 under the name. After that, the poet wrote "*I have something to say to Nightingale*" (1987), "*Iltijo*"(1988), "*Sleeping Girl*"(1989), "*Halima enam allalari*" (1989), "*Ishq kemasi*"(1990), "*Ko' There is a place in my mind*"(1990), "*There are many bewafos*"(1991), "*Yolgonshi yor*", "*Erka kiyik*"(1992), "*I will take you to my sky*" and dozens of poetry collections are available to readers. the league has arrived. He turned to major poetic genres and created epics such as "*The End of the Sky*", "*The Black Sun*". The achievement of independence of our country raised new horizons in the work of Muhammad Yusuf. His beautiful poems in honor of the nation and the country's independence echoed in the hearts of millions with their sincerity, simplicity, and artistic perfection. Dozens of the poet's poems such as "*My country*", "*Khalk bolelim*", "*Dunyo*", "*InshaAllah*", "*Uzbekmomo*", "*Ikror*", "*Tilak*" are beautiful poetry, how to sing the country became the works that proved their necessity.

Muhammad Yusuf's poetry was an important event in the literature of the 90s of the 20th century. It is true that many articles about the poet's life and work were published in the press. But most of the published articles are dedicated to the bright memory of the poet. There are only a few scientific

studies that provide a deep analysis of his work from an artistic and linguistic point of view. Muhammad Yusuf is a unique poet, and his poems are written in folk tones, so he differs sharply from the works of other poets. The study of the skill of the representatives of all fiction literature in choosing and using words is of special importance in the development of our linguistics. Through this aspect, the individual style of writers and poets is clearly visible. That's why in Uzbek linguistics, aspects such as the uniqueness of the artistic speech of our creators and the extent to which they use language tools are being studied as the main topic. Basically, prose works form the basis of the studies studied to this day. We can recognize that all these works have high scientific potential and level. It is appropriate that special attention is paid to poetic works. But increasing their number is one of the urgent problems of our linguistics. In this context, it is appropriate to mention G.Muhammadjonova's dissertation entitled "*Linguopoetic study of Uzbek poetry of the late 1980s and early 1990s*" (2003). In this work, along with the works of poets such as Shavkat Rahman, Usman Azim, Azam Oktam, Iqbal Mirza, the poetry of Muhammad Yusuf is also studied, albeit partially pragmatically⁹. This scientific work can also be a reason to study the work of the poet. Therefore, almost no attention has been paid to the deep scientific analysis of this artist's poetry. For this reason, we tried to study the poet's work and his ability to use universal expressions in his poems.

In recent years, a number of works have been carried out on researching the language of artistic works. In recent years, a number of works have been carried out on the research of pragmatic features. The methods of learning the language of an artistic work, its goals and tasks are based on different viewpoints in these works, it was also stated in the above candidacy work, for example, H. Doniyorov and S. Mirzayev showed two aspects of learning the language of an artistic work.

It is known that the words in the language differ in terms of pictoriality and expressiveness even in the case of performing the nominative task. That is, the creator will be able to enhance the expression and image without affecting the meaning of the word, only by "choosing words" from the existing vocabulary. The poet's use of words existing in his language, different from the usual situation, occurs with the following artistic and aesthetic goals:

1. *This is to give the color (spirit) of the era.*
2. *Pragmatic units used in poetry are useful for giving the color of place in an artistic work.*

⁹ Muhammadjonova G. *Linguopoetic study of Uzbek sharia of the late 80s and early 90s*: Filol.fan. candidate...authorref. T: 2004.-B.23.

3. *An artistic image has the characteristic of specificity.*

4. *Expressing a pragmatic attitude to the subject of the image.*

At this point, it is necessary to pay attention to deviations at the pragmatic level. In the process of speech, we can use words in their own sense or in a joint sense. The use of a word in a different sense from its usual meaning is considered a pragmatic deviation. The general name of the words used in a joint sense is called trope. There are a number of forms of word meaning increase, trope such as metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, irony. The stitches used in the work of art are significantly different from each other in terms of the level of use, artistic coloring, and the level of effectiveness. In conclusion, it should be said that Muhammad Yusuf is a unique poet, his poems are written in folk tones, and he differs sharply from the work of other poets. The study of the skills of all literary representatives in choosing and using words is of special importance in the development of our linguistics.

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